

Caring for our colleagues amidst backlash: A conversation guide

Anita Simha

Gaurav Kandlikar

“and when we speak we are afraid
our words will not be heard
nor welcomed
but when we are silent
we are still afraid

So it is better to speak”

– Audre Lorde, “Litany for Survival”

Context: resisting a climate of fear and silence

In the last few weeks, executive initiatives to curtail diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) have had far-reaching consequences for scientists. As a maneuver to ensure no federal dollars were funding “DEI,” NSF grant payments were briefly paused, including salaries for postdoctoral researchers, before a judge blocked the move. A leaked list of flagged words (including “historically”, “women”, and “community diversity”) that require review for NSF proposals may have seemed dark yet funny for ecologists who, in a plant, microbial, or other context, study community diversity. These events show that federal support for science is eroding, and the resilience of scientific agencies such as the NSF and NIH to this growing backlash is somewhat uncertain. At the same time, many minority groups, immigrants and trans people in particular, are bearing the brunt of a scapegoating administration. Rumors of ICE raids, news of growing anti-immigrant sentiment, bans on needed healthcare, and more may be affecting our colleagues’ wellbeing. Overall, students, staff, and faculty in ecology and evolutionary biology departments at universities across the US are feeling the effects of this backlash, albeit unevenly.

In the face of these changing conditions, academic ecologists may feel uncertain on how to best respond as individuals, and as members of labs, departments, unions, and professional societies. In particular, fear of backlash may make “speaking up” feel risky or even futile. Asking another person to “speak up” may feel loaded or unfair, whether they are an early-career researcher, busy PI or an elusive dean.

However, our perspective is that now is the time to ask more of each other and demand more from our institutions rather than less. In fact, the risk of speaking grows each day that silence becomes the norm. We believe we have a responsibility to care for each other as

members of labs and departments doing science together. Further, this responsibility extends to sharing accurate information about what is changing; at the same time that serious consequential federal actions are being implemented that target immigrants, trans people, and other marginalized groups, overestimating them may inadvertently cede ground we do not need to give. Frank and frequent conversation can serve as a corrective to freely given concessions. Several of our professional societies, including ESA, have modeled swift, straightforward, and brave initial responses to anti-science, anti-immigrant, and anti-trans executive power-wielding. In line with such statements, we encourage labs and departments to make space for open conversation on the material consequences of the current administration's actions for our professional and personal lives, and for the responses that such actions merit.

In a recent lab meeting, our lab discussed federal funding news and visa-related uncertainties, sharing information, commiserating, brainstorming, and making plans of action. We model our approach here as an adaptable guide for labs and departments looking for resources to do something similar. At the heart of our conversations has been the shared conviction that we should raise our expectations of each other within the scientific community, not lower them, in the face of unreliable support at the federal level. We hope this document can serve as a useful conversational starting point.

Guide: suggested discussion topics and questions

Getting the facts right

- What is the history of federal funding bodies like the NSF (or NIH, NOAA, NASA, etc.)? When, how, and why did they emerge and why are they being undercut now?
- Under 'normal' circumstances how does the federal funding process work, from congressional budget to a funded proposal? Any clarifications needed on the power structures within the US government that affect science funding? Which of those steps are disrupted by ongoing initiatives?
- Beyond potentially sensational headlines, what is the substance of recent executive orders (and potential judicial rulings) related to science funding? Related to the visa process, trans healthcare, or other issues that might affect members of our lab group?

Impacts on lab funding

- What projects are federally funded in our lab? Whose salaries are federally funded?
- What work can we continue amidst federal funding uncertainties?
- What other funding avenues exist for us besides federal grants?
- How can we make decision-making on internal lab or department funds more transparent?

Visa status and student safety

- What lab and departmental resources exist in case of immigration crackdowns? What resources can we circulate, create, or demand? Does the university or department already provide funds to cover visa-related costs, for example?
- Has our university administration made a statement regarding ICE visits to campus? Can we unite as a department to ask for one?
- Who can we reach out to for training for faculty, staff, and students on how to respond to an ICE visit to campus?
- What requirements, like minimum health coverage, exist for lab members' visas and the visas of their dependents? Are these university or federal requirements? What is the duration of these visas and the requirements for their renewal?
- What field safety protocols do we have in place, and what additional risks are lab members concerned about? What can we do to mitigate these risks?

Community and advocacy

- What progress towards equity have we noticed in our lab and in our department in the last decade? Since 2020? How do we make sure such progress isn't rolled back?
- Can the PI advocate at upcoming faculty meetings to secure a statement of support for immigrant students from the department leadership? Where else can we apply pressure?
- In what other ways will we each continue to live our professional and personal values out loud?
- What other organizations (grad student and faculty committees and unions, professional societies, community organizations) exist outside the lab that we are each tapped into? How can we support the activities of our broader community networks?
- Given the current political environment, how do we best advocate for science as a whole and fundamental research specifically?

Education and Introspection

- How can we educate ourselves more on the history of racist ideas and other biases in our field? What support do we need from our lab and from our department to make this sort of continued education happen?
- What can we do to learn more about how the current national climate impacts our immigrant, trans, and other marginalized colleagues, and what further actions can we take to support their personal wellbeing and professional success?

Takeaways: an example from one lab's conversation

In one case, a group of us spent a recent lab meeting discussing recent executive actions related to science funding and immigration, along with their impacts on the lab group. Overall, much of our conversation consisted of searching for information and sharing

pre-existing knowledge. We also built a deeper sense of community by sharing our experiences and commiserating. Importantly, we recognized that a single conversation would not sufficiently address our concerns. We resolved to regularly check in, especially as we make progress on our action steps and as new federal initiatives come to light. Here, we reproduce a few of our takeaways:

- *Federal funding* - Amidst sensational news headlines and changing terrain, it is important to understand the substance of what changes have taken place. We want to recognize the seriousness of federal anti-science measures, but we want to take care not to inflate those actions. Resources like the Council of Government Relations (<https://www.cogr.edu/2025-administration-transition-information-resources>), NSF's page on Implementation of Executive Orders (<https://www.nsf.gov/executive-orders>), and other regulation trackers (<https://eelp.law.harvard.edu/tracking-the-trackers/>) are useful guides. For the moment, none of the members of our lab have federally funded salaries. Although our long-term success relies on federal funding, we have some amount of certainty and freedom in the short-term. This may allow us to act as a counterbalance to labs that find themselves in a different position than ours. We want to avoid the instinct to "tone it down" in the current climate and continue to urge our department and those in our network to do the same.
- *Visa status and student safety* - Most members of our lab are not US citizens by birth, and we felt hyper-aware of that fact, especially as field scientists that frequently travel regionally. Some of us shared frustration that we simply want to do good scientific work and are having to do so in a climate of intense anxiety. We are aware that rumors of ICE visits are limiting some communities' activities, and we want to be careful to share important information without fearmongering. Multiple of us felt we did not have enough information on what to do in an emergency situation and were interested in more training. We acknowledge that immigrant grad students are on tight timelines post-graduation to find a job and stay in the US, so we want to actively support each other on the job hunt and develop reasonable graduation timelines with visa status in mind. Finally, we are committed to our lab members' safety while conducting fieldwork and will dedicate lab resources to revise our field safety plans, e.g. by referring to guides like "Field safety! an e-zine by and for trans and queer scientists" (<https://zenodo.org/records/8387594>)
- *Community* - We are connected to incredible organizations, such as the graduate student committee in our department, and we want to work with and support these groups. We want to make sure that everyone in our community feels safe and equipped to ask more of their advisors and departments.
- *Advocacy*: As a lab, we have prioritized three specific near-term actions – (1) sharing information about Black ecologists for Black History Month, (2) assembling this guide, and (3) attending and amplifying department-level conversations about our colleagues' experiences in this time. We recognize that these actions constrained to the academy will not address the broader forces at play, but we think that learning and caring for each other is an important goal. In the long-term, we remain committed to continuing these conversations and making space in our lab for more outward advocacy, for example by following the lead of Ecological Society of America's Policy

Action Alerts (<https://esa.org/esablog/2025/02/19/20457/>), which provides resources for contacting our local legislators.

- *Education* - The repeated and sustained attacks on science as a whole, and on immigrants, trans people, and other marginalized communities galvanize us to study our discipline's history to gain more understanding of our position in this political moment. As a longer-term action, we want to begin a reading seminar. We seek to welcome as many interested department members as possible to this, and we want to incentivize their participation and find a way to acknowledge time spent on this project.
- *Making asks* - We all participated in writing this manuscript and want to attach our names, but at the same time several of our lab's members feel aware of their precarious status in the US. The solution we came to – seeking as many signatories on this paper as possible – reflects a “safety in numbers” strategy. Interestingly, this solution has obligated us to practice our stated value of asking more of our community.

Supporting our community is a collective responsibility because we all have a stake in the survival and success of each other, of each other's work, and of our profession. We encourage all members of our community to voice their concerns and to hold each other, and our leaders, to high standards. We also encourage those in the community whose personal livelihoods, health, and safety have not been directly impacted to use their platform to uplift our science and our colleagues.